

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN RELIGIOSITY AND SPIRITUALITY AND SELF-REPORTED SYMPTOMS OF DEPRESSION AMONG SELECTED UNIVERSITY STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

Filipinos' public expression of their religious practices was restricted by the government during the COVID-19 pandemic as a means to limit the spread of the virus. As a traditionally religious people, this may have added to the mental and emotional burdens particularly of the youth. This study sought to ascertain the relationship between religiosity and spirituality and self-reported symptoms of depression among college students of a particular university in Antipolo City, Philippines. 86 volunteers who publicly profess a specific religious affiliation and who belong to families whose parents are both living were selected to be the participants of this study. The Religiosity and Spirituality Scale for Youth was utilized as well as the PHQ-9 instrument of Pfizer to measure the respondents' levels of self-reported depressive symptoms. It was found that females exhibited higher religiosity and spirituality than the males. Females also exhibited higher levels of self-reported depressive symptoms than males. Respondents whose parents are staying together exhibited higher religiosity and spirituality than those whose parents are separated and respondents whose parents are separated exhibited higher levels of self-reported depressive symptoms than those whose parents are staying together. The respondents without romantic involvement exhibited higher religiosity and spirituality than those with romantic involvement and respondents without romantic involvement exhibited higher levels of self-reported depressive symptoms than those with romantic involvement. A low negative relationship between Religiosity and Spirituality Scale scores and PHQ-9 scores of the respondents was established. This finding implies that higher levels of religiosity and spirituality tend to lower the incidence of mental health issues such as depression among the respondents of this study.

Keywords: Religiosity, Spirituality, Depression, PHQ-9, COVID-19, Philippines.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Mainstream of Filipinos (92%) are of the Christian Faith. Most are Roman Catholic and approximately 10% are composed of Protestant, Evangelicals, Adventist, INC and so on. The other segment of the population is mainly Muslim.¹

Being the largest Christian country in Asia, church gatherings are considered essential in the practice of one's faith. However, the arrival of the COVID-19 global pandemic created challenges to the holding of these public gatherings for a period of around 2 years because of government restrictions that attempted to mitigate the spread of the disease.²

Since the Philippines is mostly a Catholic country, it was found that Filipino Catholics utilizes religion as a coping process, especially during the pandemic and furthermore made use of their traditional values to facilitate the healing of the social fabric damaged by the isolation caused by COVID-19.³ One article asserts that the coronavirus may have hindered Filipinos from attending church but the virus will never succeed in removing their faith.⁴

However, the mental health of young Filipinos suffered dramatically during the pandemic. A study found that the number Filipino youths who experienced sadness, loneliness and dislike by others almost doubled between 2013 and 2021.⁵

In 2021, 7.5% or 1.5 million young Filipinos experienced having thought of ending their lives. Among the reasons for the poorer state of mental health among the youth are said to be understaffing of mental health professional services, the cost of consultation and therapy and the stigmatization of mental health issues.⁶

Since it has been shown that religion is utilized as a means of dealing with stressful events in life, this study sought to investigate its link to mental health. Some studies have found that religious orientations and social cognitive approaches to religion were significantly associated to well-being.⁷

A study also established that reduced health status combined with limited participation in church activities resulted in lower self-ratings in mental health and more depressive symptoms.⁸ It was also found that religiosity had a negative relationship with psychoticism.⁹ In yet another study, purpose in life scores of respondents mediated the relationships between religiosity with anxiety and depression.¹⁰

A study also found that unstable non-religious respondents who perceived God as distant were more prone to experiencing close relationship anxiety and were at greater risk of worse mental health problems.¹¹ Many studies have shown that higher levels of religiosity and spirituality were associated with better mental health in adolescents and were generally stronger for males and older individuals than for females and younger people.¹² Another study showed that religious participants found greater meaning and peace than nonreligious participants¹³ and religious people tend to be happier.¹⁴

However, a study established that it was the social interaction and emotional support that resulted from religious involvement which were the most powerful predictors of decreased hopelessness, depression, and suicide.¹⁵ Furthermore, a meta-analysis of 24 studies revealed no support for the belief that religiousness is associated with psychopathology.¹⁶

Based on the foregoing, there appears to be a slight discrepancy in the findings of the studies reviewed. And this is one of the reasons why this research was undertaken. This study attempted to discover the levels of religiosity and spirituality of college students in a private university in Antipolo City, Philippines. It also sought to ascertain their self-reported depressive symptoms. These two scores of the research participants were then correlated in order to ascertain the existence of an association between these two variables and what kind of relationship it was.

In particular, this study sought to address the following research questions:

1. What are the levels of religiosity and spirituality of the respondents when grouped according to
 - 1.1 Sex;
 - 1.2 State of parental union (living together or separated);
 - 1.3 Romantic involvement?
2. What are the levels of self-reported depressive symptoms of the respondents when grouped according to
 - 2.1 Sex;
 - 2.2 State of parental union (living together or separated);
 - 2.3 Romantic involvement?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the respondents' levels of religiosity and spirituality and their levels of self-reported depressive symptoms?

II. METHODOLOGY

Volunteers whose informed consent was first obtained and whose identities were not acquired, were asked to participate in this study from a private university in Antipolo City. The participants were then screened and only those who publicly professed a religious affiliation (non-atheists and non-agnostics), were selected. The respondents were further screened to include only those whose biological parents are alive. This resulted in a total of 86 college respondents. 28 were males and 58 were females. Their mean age was 20.55. The Religiosity and Spirituality Scale for Youth¹⁷ was utilized, which consists of 37 items. Permission to make use of the instrument was obtained from the author. Each item of the instrument is a statement to which the respondent may answer never, sometimes, mostly or always. The PHQ-9 instrument which Pfizer allows free use¹⁸ was administered to measure the respondents' levels of self-reported depressive symptoms.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The following are the data obtained presented in tabular form and the statistical treatments administered.

Table 1: Religiosity and Spirituality Scale Scores of the respondents grouped according to sex

Item	Male Weighted Mean N=28	Female Weighted Mean N=58
1. My religious beliefs make me happy.	2	2.210
2. I pray in public.	1.5933	1.5529
3. I study/read scriptures.	0.926	1.079
4. When I'm worried or nervous, my faith helps me calm down.	1.963	2.105
5. When I need help, I go to people with my same religious beliefs.	1.148	1.013
6. I attend prayer groups.	0.741	0.961
7. Praying gives me strength when I'm upset.	2.037	2.382
8. When trying to solve a problem, I ask God for help.	2.296	2.368
9. I have a close relationship with God.	1.815	2.092
10. When I do something wrong, I ask for God's forgiveness.	2.296	2.434
11. I listen to religious songs or poetry about God.	1.333	1.618
12. I talk with others about my religious beliefs	1	1.211
13. My faith gives me hope in tough times.	1.963	2.303
14. I watch religious TV shows or movies.	1.037	1.053
15. When I face a problem, I pray for God's help.	2.148	2.553
16. I spend time with kids who share my religious beliefs.	0.704	1.013
17. Knowing God is with me keeps me from feeling lonely.	1.667	2.211
18. I find teachings about God interesting or helpful.	1.741	2.105
19. My belief in God gives my life meaning.	1.923	2.421
20. I believe God will not give me more than I can handle.	2.074	2.355
21. I read books about God (other than the holy scriptures).	1.074	1.039
22. I give money based on my religious beliefs.	1.074	0.816
23. When something bad happens, I know God is trying to make me stronger.	2.259	2.316
24. I volunteer to help others based on my religious beliefs.	1.259	1.184
25. I ask other people to pray for me.	1.148	1.303
26. When bad things happen, I know God will show me the answers.	2.111	2.224

27. My beliefs about God help me decide what to do in hard situations.	1.926	2.237
28. When I'm upset, I remind myself that God loves me.	1.926	2.237
29. I confess my sins to God.	2.111	2.368
30. When I'm upset, I remind myself to be thankful for what I have.	2.185	2.382
31. When I'm struggling, I ask God to help me understand my situation.	2	2.382
32. I give others spiritual or religious advice.	1.111	1.395
33. I say scriptures to myself when I'm upset or scared.	1.037	1.079
34. When bad things happen, I try to figure out what lesson God is trying to teach me.	2.037	2.092
35. My faith gives me feelings of peacefulness.	1.889	2.197
36. I get strength and support from people in my religious community.	1.407	1.592
37. God comforts me.	2.296	2.579
Grand weighted mean	1.656	1.850

Table 2: PHQ-9 Scores of the respondents grouped according to sex

Item	Male Weighted Mean N=28	Female Weighted Mean N=58
1. Little interest or pleasure in doing things	1.519	1.526
2. Feeling down, depressed, or hopeless	1.037	1.842
3. Trouble falling or staying asleep, or sleeping too much	1.407	1.934
4. Feeling tired or having little energy	1.333	2.039
5. Poor appetite or overeating	1.000	1.645
6. Feeling bad about yourself — or that you are a failure or have let yourself or your family down	1.593	2.000
7. Trouble concentrating on things, such as reading the newspaper or watching television	1.185	1.658
8. Moving or speaking so slowly that other people could have noticed? Or the opposite — being so fidgety or restless that you have been moving around a lot more than usual	0.889	1.066
9. Thoughts that you would be better off dead or of hurting yourself in some way	0.852	1.289
Grand weighted mean	1.202	1.667

Table 3: Religiosity and Spirituality Scale Scores of the respondents grouped according to state of parental union

Item	Parents Living Together Weighted Mean N=70	Parents Separated Weighted Mean N=16
1. My religious beliefs make me happy.	2.129	1.938
2. I pray in public.	1.615	1.375
3. I study/read scriptures.	1.015	0.938
4. When I'm worried or nervous, my faith helps me calm down.	2.115	1.500
5. When I need help, I go to people with my same religious beliefs.	1.072	0.938
6. I attend prayer groups.	0.872	0.813
7. Praying gives me strength when I'm upset.	2.358	1.688
8. When trying to solve a problem, I ask God for help.	2.443	1.750
9. I have a close relationship with God.	2.014	1.875
10. When I do something wrong, I ask for God's forgiveness.	2.357	2.313
11. I listen to religious songs or poetry about God.	1.529	1.563
12. I talk with others about my religious beliefs	1.171	1.186
13. My faith gives me hope in tough times.	2.214	2.000
14. I watch religious TV shows or movies.	1.086	0.936
15. When I face a problem, I pray for God's help.	2.414	2.313
16. I spend time with kids who share my religious beliefs.	0.886	1.063
17. Knowing God is with me keeps me from feeling lonely.	2.071	1.875
18. I find teachings about God interesting or helpful.	2.029	1.875
19. My belief in God gives my life meaning.	2.314	2.125
20. I believe God will not give me more than I can handle.	2.314	1.938
21. I read books about God (other than the holy scriptures).	0.943	1.000
22. I give money based on my religious beliefs.	0.871	0.688
23. When something bad happens, I know God is trying to make me stronger.	2.300	2.125
24. I volunteer to help others based on my religious beliefs.	1.186	0.875
25. I ask other people to pray for me.	1.357	1.000
26. When bad things happen, I know God will show me the answers.	2.214	2.0625

27. My beliefs about God help me decide what to do in hard situations.	2.200	1.875
28. When I'm upset, I remind myself that God loves me.	2.228	1.687
29. I confess my sins to God.	2.271	2.250
30. When I'm upset, I remind myself to be thankful for what I have.	2.371	2.187
31. When I'm struggling, I ask God to help me understand my situation.	2.314	2.125
32. I give others spiritual or religious advice.	1.328	1.062
33. I say scriptures to myself when I'm upset or scared.	0.985	1.250
34. When bad things happen, I try to figure out what lesson God is trying to teach me.	2.085	2
35. My faith gives me feelings of peacefulness.	2.128	1.937
36. I get strength and support from people in my religious community.	1.557	1.187
37. God comforts me.	2.528	2.250
Grand weighted mean	1.807722	1.609797

Table 4: PHQ-9 Scores of the respondents grouped according to state of parental union

Item	Parents Living Together Weighted Mean N=70	Parents Separated Weighted Mean N=16
1. Little interest or pleasure in doing things	1.400	1.750
2. Feeling down, depressed, or hopeless	1.514	1.750
3. Trouble falling or staying asleep, or sleeping too much	1.700	1.875
4. Feeling tired or having little energy	1.800	1.937
5. Poor appetite or overeating	1.300	1.937
6. Feeling bad about yourself — or that you are a failure or have let yourself or your family down	1.814	2.062
7. Trouble concentrating on things, such as reading the newspaper or watching television	1.385	1.875
8. Moving or speaking so slowly that other people could have noticed? Or the opposite — being so fidgety or restless that you have been moving around a lot more than usual	0.885	1.437
9. Thoughts that you would be better off dead or of hurting yourself in some way	1.085	1.437
Grand weighted mean	1.432	1.785

Table 5: Religiosity and Spirituality Scale Scores of the respondents grouped according to romantic involvement

Item	With Romantic Involvement Weighted Mean N=35	Without Romantic Involvement Weighted Mean N=51
1. My religious beliefs make me happy.	2.085	2.098
2. I pray in public.	1.514	1.607
3. I study/read scriptures.	0.942	1.039
4. When I'm worried or nervous, my faith helps me calm down.	2.114	1.921
5. When I need help, I go to people with my same religious beliefs.	1.057	1.039
6. I attend prayer groups.	0.857	0.862
7. Praying gives me strength when I'm upset.	2.371	2.137
8. When trying to solve a problem, I ask God for help.	2.200	2.392
9. I have a close relationship with God.	1.914	2.039
10. When I do something wrong, I ask for God's forgiveness.	2.314	2.372
11. I listen to religious songs or poetry about God.	1.600	1.490
12. I talk with others about my religious beliefs	1.200	1.156
13. My faith gives me hope in tough times.	2.114	2.215
14. I watch religious TV shows or movies.	1.085	1.039
15. When I face a problem, I pray for God's help.	2.371	2.411
16. I spend time with kids who share my religious beliefs.	0.742	1.039
17. Knowing God is with me keeps me from feeling lonely.	1.800	2.196
18. I find teachings about God interesting or helpful.	1.942	2.039
19. My belief in God gives my life meaning.	2.285	2.274
20. I believe God will not give me more than I can handle.	2.257	2.235
21. I read books about God (other than the holy scriptures).	0.885	1.000
22. I give money based on my religious beliefs.	0.771	0.882
23. When something bad happens, I know God is trying to make me stronger.	2.342	2.215
24. I volunteer to help others based on my religious beliefs.	1.028	1.196
25. I ask other people to pray for me.	1.200	1.352
26. When bad things happen, I know God will show me the	2.228	2.156

answers.		
27. My beliefs about God help me decide what to do in hard situations.	2.171	2.117
28. When I'm upset, I remind myself that God loves me.	2.057	2.176
29. I confess my sins to God.	2.228	2.294
30. When I'm upset, I remind myself to be thankful for what I have.	2.428	2.274
31. When I'm struggling, I ask God to help me understand my situation.	2.257	2.294
32. I give others spiritual or religious advice.	1.285	1.274
33. I say scriptures to myself when I'm upset or scared.	1.057	1.019
34. When bad things happen, I try to figure out what lesson God is trying to teach me.	2.114	2.039
35. My faith gives me feelings of peacefulness.	2.000	2.156
36. I get strength and support from people in my religious community.	1.400	1.549
37. God comforts me.	2.457	2.490
Grand weighted mean	1.748	1.786

Table 6: PHQ-9 Scores of the respondents grouped according to romantic involvement

Item	With Romantic Involvement Weighted Mean N=35	Without Romantic Involvement Weighted Mean N=51
1. Little interest or pleasure in doing things	1.428	1.490
2. Feeling down, depressed, or hopeless	1.571	1.549
3. Trouble falling or staying asleep, or sleeping too much	1.771	1.705
4. Feeling tired or having little energy	1.685	1.921
5. Poor appetite or overeating	1.257	1.529
6. Feeling bad about yourself — or that you are a failure or have let yourself or your family down	1.742	1.941
7. Trouble concentrating on things, such as reading the newspaper or watching television	1.542	1.431
8. Moving or speaking so slowly that other people could have noticed? Or the opposite — being so fidgety or restless that you have been moving around a lot more than usual	0.857	1.078
9. Thoughts that you would be better off dead or of hurting yourself in some way	1.200	1.117
Grand weighted mean	1.450794	1.529412

Table 7: Relationship between Religiosity and Spirituality and PHQ-9 Scores

Pearson r Computation	
<p>X Values</p> <p>$\Sigma = 5635$</p> <p>Mean = 65.523</p> <p>$\Sigma(X - Mx)^2 = SSx = 44423.453$</p> <p>Y Values</p> <p>$\Sigma = 1159$</p> <p>Mean = 13.477</p> <p>$\Sigma(Y - My)^2 = SSy = 3725.453$</p>	<p>X and Y Combined</p> <p>N = 86</p> <p>$\Sigma(X - Mx)(Y - My) = -2749.453$</p> <p>R Calculation</p> <p>$r = \frac{\Sigma((X - My)(Y - Mx))}{\sqrt{(SSx)(SSy)}}$</p> <p>$r = -2749.453 / \sqrt{((44423.453)(3725.453))} = -0.2137$</p>
<p>r = -0.2137</p> <p>low negative relationship</p>	

Table 1 shows the weighted means for each of the 37 items of the Religiosity and Spirituality Scale of the respondents grouped according to sex. There are 28 males and 58 females. The grand weighted mean of the females is relatively higher than the males. It can be inferred from this that females exhibit higher religiosity and spirituality than the males for this particular group of respondents.

Table 2 shows the weighted means for each of the 9 items of the PHQ-9 questionnaire of the respondents grouped according to sex. The grand weighted mean of the females is relatively higher than the males. It can be inferred from this that females exhibit higher levels of self-reported depressive symptoms than males for this particular group of respondents.

Table 3 shows the weighted means for each of the 37 items of the Religiosity and Spirituality Scale of the respondents grouped according to state of parental union. There are 70 respondents whose parents are staying together and there are 16 whose parents are separated. The grand weighted mean of the respondents whose parents are staying together is relatively higher than the those whose parents are separated. It can be inferred from this that respondents whose parents are staying together exhibit higher religiosity and spirituality than those whose parents are separated for this particular group of respondents.

Table 4 shows the weighted means for each of the 9 items of the PHQ-9 questionnaire of the respondents grouped according to state of parental union. The grand weighted mean of the respondents whose parents are separated is relatively higher than those whose parents are staying together. It can be inferred from this that respondents whose parents are separated exhibit higher levels of self-reported depressive symptoms than those whose parents are staying together for this particular group of respondents.

Table 5 shows the weighted means for each of the 37 items of the Religiosity and Spirituality Scale of the respondents grouped according to romantic involvement. There are 35 respondents with romantic involvement and there are 51 without romantic involvement. The grand weighted mean of the respondents without romantic involvement is relatively higher than the with romantic involvement. It can be inferred from this that respondents without romantic involvement exhibit higher religiosity and spirituality than those with romantic involvement for this particular group of respondents.

Table 6 shows the weighted means for each of the 9 items of the PHQ-9 questionnaire of the respondents grouped according to romantic involvement. The grand weighted mean of the respondents without romantic involvement is relatively higher than those with romantic involvement. It can be inferred from this that respondents without romantic involvement exhibit higher levels of self-reported depressive symptoms than those with romantic involvement for this particular group of respondents.

Table 7 shows the Pearson r computation of the Religiosity and Spirituality Scale scores and PHQ-9 scores of the respondents. An r value of -0.2137 was obtained. This indicates a low negative relationship between Religiosity and Spirituality Scale scores and PHQ-9 scores of the respondents. This implies that higher

Religiosity and Spirituality Scale scores will tend to yield somewhat lower PHQ-9 scores for the respondents, and vice-versa.

IV. CONCLUSION

For this particular set of respondents, it was observed that females exhibited higher religiosity and spirituality than the males. Females also exhibited higher levels of self-reported depressive symptoms than males. Respondents whose parents are staying together exhibited higher religiosity and spirituality than those whose parents are separated and respondents whose parents are separated exhibited higher levels of self-reported depressive symptoms than those whose parents are staying together. The respondents without romantic involvement exhibited higher religiosity and spirituality than those with romantic involvement and respondents without romantic involvement exhibited higher levels of self-reported depressive symptoms than those with romantic involvement. However, it must be stressed that these comparisons were based on unequal group sizes and that tests of significant difference were not done on the scores.

The low negative relationship found between Religiosity and Spirituality Scale scores and PHQ-9 scores of the respondents is consistent with most of the studies cited herein. Higher levels of religiosity and spirituality tend to lower the incidence of mental health issues such as depression. Further studies among Filipinos are recommended to ascertain whether such a relationship is also true for other forms of mental health issues.

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DECLARATION

The authors declare that the ethical standards of research were strictly followed and that there was no conflict of interest in the conduct of this study.

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